

Online Database of Sustainable Trade Case Studies

MATS Deliverable 3.2

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www.sustainable-agri-trade.eu

Summary

Deliverable D3.2 is focused on the design, development and deployment of the MATS Case Study Database, providing detailed information on the concept, methodology and objectives of the 15 MATS studies.

The present report accompanies this deployment of the MATS use case database, describing the involved datapoints and reporting on the technologies, workflows, and user-facing assets used for implementing the database and exposing its contents to end-users. The architectural design and infrastructural choices allow for the database to be seamlessly and to a large extent automatically accept new or updated input, thus ensuring the relevant information is timely delivered to MATS audiences.

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¹ R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² PU = Public, CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Introduction

The goal of WP3, *Assessing Linkages*, is to provide a comprehensive in-depth assessment of the linkages between agricultural trade, agricultural and rural investments, environmental sustainability and human well-being. This includes a set of 15 case studies to provide a deeper understanding of trade impacts at local market and societal level, and how these shape national, regional and global socioeconomic and environmental trends.

To make the results of the case studies actionable and ensure their broad availability and outreach, a database for storing the relevant information in a structured, processable way is designed, along with applications and components that consume the database and present the information to MATS target audiences in a clear, interactive fashion.

The present document provides information on the design and implementation of the components involved in the database creation and management, along with an overview of the user-facing applications serving case study data to the end users.

The MATS Case Studies Database

To build the MATS Case Studies Database, we put in place a comprehensive workflow that incorporates the gathering of information from the Case Study leaders, the pre-processing of the collected data, and their ingestion in the relevant persistent storage mechanism integrated in the MATS data platform. To collect the information, a shared Microsoft Excel™ spreadsheet with a well-defined structure was made available to case study representatives, who filled in the relevant information for their studies in accordance with the instructions provided by SCiO personnel. The structure of the spreadsheet is informed by a concrete study description model, which defines the core descriptive features of a study. The model, along with the vocabularies of terms used for categorical features, are presented in the following subsections.

Case Study Description Model

TABLE 1: CASE STUDY DESCRIPTION MODEL

Property name	Type	Cardinality	Description
ID	Integer	1	The unique identifier of the case study
Country	Controlled Terms	1*	The country/countries relevant to the case study
Continent	Controlled Terms	1*	The continent(s) relevant to the case study – automatically inferred by country information
SDG	Controlled Terms	1*	The Sustainable Development Goals to which the case study contributes
Product	Controlled Terms	1*	The commodity/commodities addressed by the case study
Focus	Controlled Terms	1*	The trade facet(s) relevant to the case study
Methodology	Controlled Terms	1*	The scientific approach applied for implementing the case study
Topic	Controlled Terms	1*	From GA
Title	Text	1	The title of the case study
URL	URL	1	A link to the case study description in the MATS website
Image	URL	0:1	A link to an image representative for the case study
Summary	Text	1	A brief description of the subject, scope, objectives and methods of the case study
Main Question(s)	Text	1*	The key hypotheses tested by the study

Approach	Text	1	A high-level description of the methods, tools, and processes adopted for implementing the case study
Expected Impact	Text	1	Key expected outcomes from the study
Leader	Text	1	The organisational entity leading the implementation of the study
Local Partner(s)	Text	0*	Partners active and situated in the countries covered by the study, which participate in some capacity to the study's implementation

Controlled Term Lists

TABLE 2: VOCABULARIES OF TERMS FOR CATEGORICAL FEATURES

Product
Beef
Biofuels
Cacao
Coffee
Dairy
Food products
Milk
Milk powder
Oats
Pork
Poultry
Wine
Focus
Market & investments
Social Resilience/Human rights
Environmental
Trade policy & Governance
Methodology
Value chain mapping and analysis
Participatory qualitative research
Analysis of publicly available macro-economic statistics, current legislations, existing studies, and triangulation
System dynamics and other simulation modelling tools
Other
Methodology
Agrifood international trade, trade agreements among Europe and Africa, role of consumption trends, position of farmers in agricultural markets and FVC

Climate-change related risks for sustainable trade, and the role of and interplay with biodiversity agreements
Role of territorial approaches in more resilient sustainable and fair food systems
Sustainable business models
Climate-change related risks and resilience, deforestation, and the role of biodiversity agreements
EU climate and energy policies and their influence on investments, trade and land use change
Policy, biodiversity and ecosystem services provision
Sustainable Development Goals
SDG1: No Poverty
SDG2: Zero Hunger
SDG3: Good Health and Well-Being
SDG4: Quality Education
SDG5: Gender Equality
SDG6: Clean Water and Sanitation
SDG7: Affordable and Clean Energy
SDG8: Decent Work and Economic Growth
SDG9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
SDG10: Reduced Inequalities
SDG11: Sustainable Cities and Communities
SDG12: Responsible Consumption and Production
SDG13: Climate Action
SDG14: Life below Water
SDG15: Life on Land
SDG16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions
SDG17: Partnerships for the Goals

Data Ingestion Architecture

The Microsoft Excel™ file containing the finalized case study descriptions is securely stored online and accessible via a persistent URL. The content of the file is consumed by different connectors for the different data exposure mechanisms foreseen in MATS. Namely, the following connectors have been implemented:

- a. A Relational Database Transformer, which parses the file and populates the database integrated in the MATS website.
- b. A PowerBI connector, which accesses the file and applies transformations for preparing the data for consumption from the MATS PowerBI Dashboard. The transformed data is subsequently integrated in the

Dashboard Report described in the next section of the present document.

These different transformations of the case study data inform the discovery functions over the MATS data, either via the project's website or via the MATS Dashboard, presented below.

Case Study Discovery Functionalities

Case study data are available via the MATS website, under the relevant Cases Studies section.

The MATS website provides two initiation points for discovering and perusing information on the studies: the Case Study Overview, and the Case Study Browse modes.

Case Studies Overview

The first access mode for case study data is the Overview List, accessed via the [Overview](#) sub-menu option. It presents the list of case studies comprising some basic information (see Fig. 1) and links to a more detailed, structured description for each individual study, the *Case Study Page*.

Case Studies Overview				
Number	Topic	Key aspects	Main focus	Leading partner(s)
1.	Effects of trade on commercialisation and processing of food products	Improving the livelihoods of smallholder farmers through trade and food value chains; localisation of food systems, strengthening of territorial markets	Uganda, Tanzania	University Helsinki with Moshi Co-operative University and Makerere University
2.	Trade, resilience and social sustainability: oats value chains in the Nordics	Resilience of trade-dependent food value chains in the context of intra-EU agri-food trade and social sustainability; sustainability and equity	Finland, Sweden, EU	University Helsinki
3.	Trade, sustainability and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production	Mapping the linkages of dairy production and dairy trade with environmental externalities and production of ecosystem services	Finland, EU, trade partners	University Helsinki
4.	Accessing export markets with high quality/social/environmental standards	Standards and market access; challenges related to WTO Rules and Regulations and/or EU requirements; strengthening of territorial markets	Sub-Saharan Africa	Economic and Social Research Foundation
5.	Role of agricultural inputs and policy regulation in sustainable value chains	Emerging markets; poultry chains; role of policy regulation regarding animal welfare, inputs and trade; competitiveness, sustainability, livelihoods	Ghana	Technical University of Madrid
6.	Farm gate prices and sustainable business models: towards living income	Experiences, obstacles, impact and lessons learned from a multistakeholder initiative on sustainability standards in the cacao sector	EU, Côte d'Ivoire	Oxfam Wereldwinkels

FIGURE 1: CASE STUDIES OVERVIEW LIST

The case study page includes a more extensive description for the study, i.e., the *Case Study Profile*, along with its linkages to relevant Sustainable Development Goals. The Case Study Profile incorporates the following information points for each study:

- a. Case Study Title
- b. Case Study Leader (Person, Organisation, Contact Information)
- c. Case Study Local Partner(s): participants from institutions and organisations local to the geographical scope of the study
- d. Geographical focus and scale
- e. Product and market focus
- f. Key stakeholders
- g. Main questions addressed by the case study
- h. Short description
- i. Key relevant government/legal/institutional frameworks
- j. Key relevant policy frameworks
- k. Relevant competitiveness-related issues
- l. Methodology
- m. Data collection methodology
- n. Expected Impact

These are organised in conceptual panels within the Case Study Overview page, which allows users to quickly obtain information on the study and its aforementioned features.

Case Study Leader
University of Helsinki,
Department of Economics and
Management

UNIVERSITY OF HELSINKI

[Read More](#)

Leading Partner(s)
Moshi Co-operative University

Moshi Co-operative University

[Visit Site](#)

Makerere University

MAKERERE UNIVERSITY

[Visit Site](#)

SDG's Addressed

1 No poverty, 2 Zero hunger, 3 Good health and well-being, 6 Clean water and sanitation, 13 Climate action, 15 Life on land

Geographical Focus and Scale

Uganda
Tanzania

Main question/s addressed

How do the two case study areas differ in respect of the

- organization of value chains?
- position of smallholder farmers in chains?
- access to local, national, regional and international markets?
- impacts of different value chain arrangements on farm incomes?

What can we learn from these differences and what are the implications for trade regimes and policy?

Short description

The short description of the two regions shows why it is crucial to understand the connections with and the dynamics and intricacies of global value chains. Local markets are also characterized by new consumer demands due to changing lifestyles and increased knowledge. Related to domestic markets, the study seeks to comprehend the role of each actor in the coffee chain to ensure equal benefits to all, and consequently to support smallholder farmers in getting out of poverty.

Key governance / legal / institutional frameworks that play a role in this case

Thematic focus is the opportunities local, national, regional and international markets provide for commercialization, VCs and primary processing of coffee and the impact different strategies could have on poverty reduction. Efforts to alleviate poverty should focus on, among other things, trade and participation of smallholder farmers in value chains and access to (international) markets.

Co-operative models are believed to play a key role in providing smallholder farmers access to markets and obtain higher prices. Co-operatives can improve market participation of smallholder farmers, increase farm incomes and reduce rural poverty.

FIGURE 2: CASE STUDY #1 PROFILE PAGE

Search and Browse

The second access mode allows the filtering of case studies based on two core properties. The commodity examined in the study, and the Sustainable Development Goal to which a study contributes. The two browsing options are available via the respective [Browse by Commodity](#) and [Browse by SDG](#) menu options.

In the first case, users select their commodity of interest from the relevant dropdown menu, and the list of visible case studies is accordingly filtered to include the ones focusing on the selected commodity. Clicking on a case study panel leads again to the Case Study Profile page.

FIGURE 3: BROWSE BY COMMODITY INTERFACE

In the second case, an SDG grid is presented to the users, from where they are called to select their SDG of interest.

FIGURE 4: BROWSE BY SDG INTERFACE

Subsequently, a case study list relevant to the selected SDG is displayed, with basic info on each case study and a link to its case study profile.

FIGURE 5: CASE STUDIES FILTERED BY SDG

Interactive Dashboard

The final and most detailed mode for accessing and filtering MATS Case Studies information is the [MATS Interactive Dashboard](#). As discussed, the dashboard is informed by the case study tabular data, with the transformation and curation components required for consumption by the dashboard implemented in PowerBI. When changes or additions are made in the original spreadsheet, data are automatically refreshed in the dashboard. Refreshes are set to a daily frequency, i.e. the dashboard is updated with the new data after a maximum of 24 hours.

The main page of the dashboard presents selected aggregate data for the submitted case studies, along with the available filters for selecting subsets of the case study database according to various criteria. The presented aggregations are:

1. Distribution of case studies by continent
2. Distribution by GA Topic
3. Distribution by Study Focus

4. Distribution by relevant commodity
5. Distribution by covered SDG
6. Distribution by country

FIGURE 6: MATS INTERACTIVE DASHBOARD - MAIN PAGE

Similarly, the database can be filtered by:

1. Continent
2. Country
3. Topic
4. Focus
5. Commodity
6. Methodology
7. SDG

FIGURE 7: MATS INTERACTIVE DASHBOARD - FILTER BY COUNTRY

The second page of the dashboard showcases the subset of the case studies pool that satisfies the constraints set by the filters, with an information box for each study.

FIGURE 8: MATS INTERACTIVE DASHBOARD - STUDY INFOBOXES

When clicking on an infobox, the full summary for the selected case study appears, while the link View study details leading to the Study Profile page is activated.

FIGURE 9: MATS INTERACTIVE DASHBOARD - STUDY SUMMARY

Conclusion

The present report accompanies the deployment of the MATS use case database, describing the involved datapoints and reporting on the technologies, workflows, and user-facing assets used for implementing the database and exposing its contents to end-users. The architectural design and infrastructural choices allow for the database to be seamlessly and to a large extent automatically accept new or updated input, thus ensuring the relevant information is timely delivered to MATS audiences. Furthermore, the dynamic MATS Case Study Database presented here is also interlinked with our ongoing work on dialogue, dissemination and exploitation ([D6.1 Information needs of key actors](#), [D6.2 Enhanced engagement strategy and civil society-stakeholder-policy dialogue](#) and [D6.3 Evidence-based communication platform: Sustainable Trade Hub](#)), maximizing the visibility and usefulness of the Case Study work provided.